
The Influence of Islamic Preaching Videos on YouTube on the Formation of Noble Character Among Da'wah Management Students at IAIN Parepare

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to analyze the usage patterns and influence of Islamic preaching videos on YouTube on the formation of noble character among Da'wah Management students at IAIN Parepare. This research employs a survey method with a quantitative approach. Data collection utilizes questionnaires. The population in this study consists of 104 students, and the sampling technique used is total sampling method, where all members of the population serve as samples, totaling 104 students from the 2022 to 2024 cohorts. The research location is at IAIN Parepare among Da'wah Management students. The data analysis techniques employed include simple linear regression test, correlation test, and coefficient of determination analysis test. The research findings indicate that the majority of students tend to watch Islamic preaching videos regularly. The level of student attention toward Islamic preaching videos reaches 78.5%, demonstrating that they not only watch but also pay attention to the content presented. Furthermore, 78.65% of students acknowledge internalizing the Islamic preaching content in the videos they watch, reflecting emotional engagement and understanding of the values conveyed. The frequency of watching Islamic preaching videos is recorded at 71.16%, while the viewing duration reaches 71.25%, indicating that this activity has become part of their religious and spiritual routine. Variations in frequency and duration depend on individual interests and each student's spiritual needs. Based on the calculated t-value of 2.881, which is greater than the table t-value of 1.983, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Meanwhile, the significance value of $0.005 < 0.05$ indicates that the Islamic preaching video variable influences the formation of noble character (Y). The implications of this research encompass both practical and theoretical aspects. From a practical perspective, it is hoped that Da'wah Management students at IAIN Parepare can use YouTube social media wisely and consider the benefits of using YouTube as a medium for Islamic preaching. From a theoretical standpoint, the results of this research can be used as a reference in developing effective and efficient preaching programs for Da'wah Management students.

Keywords: Da'wah, YouTube, Noble Character

INTRUDUCTION

The Internet is a new medium that has emerged in society to provide freedom in accessing information. Supported by the presence of smartphones, information can be accessed anywhere and anytime by all users without spatial and temporal limitations. One of the internet services widely used by society is social media.

Social media serves as a platform used by users to conduct social relationships, including the formation of values, morals, and ethics (Nasrullah, 2015). Therefore, the role of social media as a communication medium becomes extremely important, influential, and significant. In Indonesia itself, social media has gained widespread popularity among both older and younger generations. Even in the current era, underage children are highly proficient in using social media (Usrina, 2021).

The emergence of social media has caused societal behavior to experience several shifts in existing culture, ethics, and norms. According to Ardianto, social media possesses social power that can shape public opinion, attitudes, and behaviors developing in society (Ardianto, 2011). Furthermore, research conducted by Lisda Waty Harianja entitled "The Influence of Social Media on Social Change in Society" demonstrates that social media has become a major force influencing social change within society. With easy and rapid access, social media has transformed the way society communicates, expanded social networks, and influenced societal views and behaviors (Harianja, 2024).

Social media encompasses many types of applications such as YouTube, TikTok, Line, Instagram, and Facebook. One of the most trending media platforms today is YouTube. According to research conducted by Slice in 2024, YouTube is the social media platform that occupies the first position as the most widely used by Indonesian society. The following is Slice's data on social media users in Indonesia for January 2024 (Slice, 2024).

YouTube enables its users to upload, watch, and share videos. Many people consider YouTube as a talent outlet; however, some members of society also utilize this platform as a creative venue for producing Islamic preaching content (Djamali & Latifah, 2016). One of the creative approaches employed to develop, introduce, and bring Islamic preaching closer to society is by uploading recorded Islamic study videos to the YouTube social media platform.

Islamic preaching (dakwah), as an activity of inviting and practicing Islamic teachings, has now found fertile ground in the realm of social media, particularly YouTube (Briandana et al., 2020). This phenomenon has given rise to millennial preachers who skillfully utilize the platform to spread religious messages, reaching broader audiences, including the millennial generation who tend to be more active in cyberspace (Mawasti & Surya, 2023). The development of information and communication technology has transformed how humans interact, learn, and obtain information (Kasir & Awali, 2024; Mawasti & Surya, 2023). Islamic preaching, which was initially conducted face-to-face, can now reach wider audiences through digital platforms such as YouTube (Kasir & Awali, 2024). Digital platforms enable the delivery of religious messages in more creative and innovative ways, adapting to diverse audiences with different preferences (Kasir & Awali, 2024).

Research findings conducted by Aflah Zuhrotul Aini on "The Influence of E-Dakwah DAQU Movie on YouTube on the Enhancement of Islamic Knowledge among UINSA Surabaya Students" indicate that the more frequently someone watches DAQU Movie's Islamic preaching content on

YouTube, the more influential it becomes on improving the Islamic understanding of UINSA Surabaya students (Aini, 2018).

Therefore, YouTube media can be utilized as a medium for conducting Islamic preaching activities because it is capable of influencing audiences. Furthermore, communication is one of the factors contributing to the emergence of influence from the Islamic preaching material delivered. Communicators can provide understanding to audiences, thereby generating communication effects.

When someone accesses and watches Islamic preaching videos on YouTube accounts, a process of seeing, reading, and listening occurs, and it is within this process that mass communication is said to take place. If this interaction activity is frequently performed, it will have a significant influence on an individual's ideology or thought patterns. Therefore, when a preacher (da'i) wishes to deliver Islamic preaching messages to communicants and wants the dakwah message to be effectively conveyed to the audience (mad'u), the delivery concept must be well-structured, starting from the target to be achieved, the content of the Islamic preaching message to be delivered, the tools used in conveying the Islamic preaching message, and the results generated from the delivered Islamic preaching message.

In communication science, the Islamic preaching message is a message, namely symbols. Etymologically, the word dakwah derives from the words da'a, yad'u, da'watan, which means to call, invite, summon, or extend an invitation. The term "Islamic preaching message" is considered more appropriate for explaining the content of dakwah in the form of words, images, drawings, and other elements that are expected to provide understanding and even bring about changes in the attitudes and behaviors of dakwah recipients. Meanwhile, the terminological definition of dakwah is an effort and invitation to the path of truth or the path of God. Even within this perspective, invitations and calls are not termed dakwah unless they are intended to lead humans to the path of goodness (Ridwan, 2018).

YouTube accounts that frequently disseminate Islamic preaching include Tafaquh Video, Yufid TV, Lampu Islam, Akhyar TV, Shift Channel, Ruziqa TV, Rodja TV, Yusuf Mansur Channel, Adi Hidayat Official, Das'ad Latif, and Ustadz Abdul Somad Official. All of these YouTube accounts actively distribute Islamic preaching videos daily, making YouTube as a medium for Islamic preaching a positive aspect or benefit that can be directly experienced by users. This strengthens the rationale for using YouTube as a new communication medium for various activities that can be conducted.

Islamic preaching videos represent one method of delivering messages that simultaneously stimulate both sight and hearing. This format has been implemented across television media, video, interactive multimedia, and various other media types. The development of Islamic preaching videos is greatly influenced by advances in internet technology and mobile devices. Islamic preachers such as Ustad Abdul Somad and Ustad Adi Hidayat utilize YouTube as a platform to deliver Islamic preaching messages to audiences. Through Islamic preaching videos, both can communicate religious messages in a more interactive and engaging manner, making them more easily accepted by

society. YouTube accounts are designed with casual, creative, and attractive styles, enabling them to present religious messages that are not monotonous. This makes Islamic preaching videos on YouTube one of the effective means for disseminating and strengthening religious values in the current digital era (Marti, Nuzuli, & Firtanosa, 2023).

One of the primary targets of YouTube Islamic preaching is students, who constitute the main actors or largest users of the YouTube application. This is also because their generation is in a period of seeking their identity and readily accepts the information they receive. In exploring religious information, students possess high religious curiosity toward realistic and easily understood religious teachings through YouTube Islamic preaching accounts that are deliberately designed to be casual, attractive, creative, and engaging. When someone increasingly accesses Islamic preaching videos on YouTube, their religious knowledge expands, which influences the formation of their noble character. Noble character is defined as a fundamental principle in Islamic teachings. Humans are required to possess noble character in comparison to other creatures of Allah SWT. This is because humans have five senses and reasoning that enable them to choose, assess, and distinguish between good, bad, and wrong actions in life (Hassan Mydin, Muhamad Shukri, & Abdul Razak, 2020). Therefore, when someone frequently accesses Islamic preaching videos on YouTube, it can indirectly influence their thought patterns and religious ideology. In other words, religious knowledge obtained through Islamic preaching videos on YouTube can impact noble character development. Islamic preaching videos on YouTube offer flexibility and accessibility, enabling Da'wah Management students at IAIN Parepare to be exposed to various Islamic perspectives, religious sermons, and studies relevant to their daily lives (Briandana et al., 2020).

The phenomenon of YouTube Islamic preaching accounts is also expected to provide educational information about Islamic teachings, Islamic religious thought ideology in a proper and correct manner, and effectively impact behavior that aligns with Islamic religious teachings. The researcher observes that many students, particularly Da'wah Management students within IAIN Parepare, utilize YouTube media as a tool to obtain information regarding Islamic preaching videos on YouTube with the purpose of developing beneficial ideas and also emulating good practices to apply in their daily lives. Therefore, this serves as the background that motivates the researcher to choose the title "The Influence of Islamic Preaching Videos on YouTube on the Formation of Noble Character Among Da'wah Management Students at IAIN Parepare."

Cognitive psychology theory, as an important part of cognitive science, has made a significant contribution to the development of educational psychology by emphasizing internal mental processes such as motivation, beliefs, and decision-making. Cognitive experts argue that human behavior cannot be measured or explained without considering mental aspects, in contrast to behaviorism, which is considered incomplete because it overlooks psychological processes such as thinking, reasoning, and emotional dimensions (Pahliwandari, 2016).

Cognitive psychology has a broad scope, encompassing mental processes such as perception, memory, attention, language, problem-solving, creativity, decision-making, and reasoning.

Additionally, this field also studies cognitive development throughout life, human intelligence, artificial intelligence, as well as various other aspects of the mind and consciousness (Jaarvis, 2022).

Cognition derives from the word "knowledge" (similar to "sciado" in Latin). According to Piaget, cognition refers to the mental activity of understanding the world. Chaplin defines it as a field of psychology that includes mental processes such as comprehension, attention, information processing, problem-solving, as well as aspects of intention and belief. Additionally, the cognitive domain is also related to will (conation) and emotion (feeling), which are connected to sensory experiences (Ujang, 2016). Some cognitive stages include attention, comprehension, memory, retrieval, and application.

Morality is a term commonly used in Indonesia, although it originates from Arabic (اخلاق). In Indonesian, akhlak refers to character, manners, politeness, decency, or etiquette. According to Hamzah Ya'qub, akhlak is identical to behavior or conduct. The Islamic Religious Terms Dictionary (KIAI) also defines akhlak linguistically as a person's actions or habits (Suhayib, 2006). Akhlakul karimah means noble or praiseworthy character that arises from good qualities in accordance with the teachings of Allah SWT and His Messenger (Badruzzaman, 2004).

In Islamic teachings, there are many verses in the Quran and sayings of the Prophet (hadith) that discuss akhlak. As mentioned in the verse of Allah in QS. Al-Ahzab/33:21.

لَقَدْ كَانَ لَكُمْ فِي رَسُولِ اللَّهِ أُسْوَةٌ حَسَنَةٌ لِّمَن كَانَ يَرْجُوا اللَّهَ وَالْيَوْمَ الْآخِرَ وَذَكَرَ اللَّهَ كَثِيرًا ۚ ٢١

The translation is:

Indeed, in the Messenger of Allah, you have a good example for those who hope for (the mercy of) Allah and (the coming of) the Day of Judgment, and who remember Allah much. (Departemen Agama RI, 2009).

The hypothesis of this research is that there is a significant influence of Islamic preaching videos on the formation of noble character among Da'wah Management students at IAIN Parepare.

The objective of this research is to analyze the usage patterns and influence of YouTube Islamic preaching videos on the formation of noble character among Da'wah Management students at IAIN Parepare.

METODE PENELITIAN

This research employs a quantitative approach. The method used is causal associative, which aims to determine the presence or absence of influence or relationship between independent variables and dependent variables, as well as the strength of the influence or relationship and whether the influence or relationship is significant (Sugiyono, 2016). In the context of this research, it seeks to find the relationship between one variable and another, namely the independent variable of YouTube Islamic preaching videos and the dependent variable of noble character.

The population in this study consists of 104 students from the Da'wah Management Study Program, Faculty of Ushuluddin, Adab, and Da'wah, IAIN Parepare from the 2022-2024 cohorts. The sampling technique employs a total sampling method, where all members of the population

serve as samples, resulting in a research sample of 104 participants. Data collection utilizes questionnaires. The research design employs a survey method with the purpose of providing a research framework used to supply information related to prevalence, distribution, and relationships between variables within a population (Sugiyono, 2016). The research instrument uses a Likert scale to measure attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of individuals or groups regarding social phenomena (Sugiyono, 2016). The data analysis techniques employed include simple linear regression test, correlation test, and coefficient of determination analysis test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Data Instrument Results

Based on the results of research instrument data analysis, the distribution of respondent responses to the studied variables can be identified. The average score method is used to interpret response tendencies, with assessment categories divided into four levels, ranging from 'very high' to 'very low.' The following is the measurement tool for respondent responses to the research variables:

Response Value

1. 76-100% (Very High)
2. 51-75% (High)
3. 26-50% (Low)
4. 0-25% (Very Low)

Table 1. Respondents' Responses to the Attention Variable

SS	S	TS	STS	JM L		SCOR E	AVERAGE SCORE	AVERAGE PERCENTAGE	CATEGORY
39	31	22	12	104		305	2.93	76,25%	Very High
41	50	5	6	104		333	3.20	83,25%	Very High
35	39	17	13	104		304	2.92	76%	Very High
Rata-Rata Skor Perhatian								78,5%	Very High

Source: Data processed using SPSS 26

In the first question, 39 respondents expressed strong agreement, and 31 respondents expressed agreement with an average percentage of 76.25%, indicating that they are more interested in watching Islamic preaching videos on YouTube than on other social media platforms. Meanwhile, 22 respondents answered disagree, and 12 respondents answered strongly disagree. This suggests that respondents may prefer other platforms due to practicality and lighter Islamic preaching delivery styles that align with their video consumption patterns.

In the second question, 41 respondents expressed strong agreement in this category, showing a very high level of interest in the visual design they encounter on YouTube. 50 respondents expressed agreement with an average percentage of 83.25%, which also reflects positive perception, though not as strong as the previous category. 6 respondents expressed disagreement, indicating they feel less attracted to the visual design presented. And 7 respondents answered disagree, representing the group that is completely unimpressed with the visual design in YouTube videos.

In the third question, 35 respondents expressed strong agreement, demonstrating a high level of concentration and deep interest in the content of videos watched. 39 respondents expressed agreement with an average percentage of 76%, showing a positive attitude, although not as strong as the previous category. 17 respondents expressed disagreement, indicating that respondents feel they do not pay much attention to details. And 13 respondents expressed strong disagreement, meaning these respondents do not pay attention to details in videos at all.

Based on the recapitulation of results conducted on three indicators within the attention variable, a final percentage of 78.5% was obtained, indicating that the respondents' attention level falls within the very high category.

Table 2. Respondents' Responses to the Appreciation Variable

SS	S	TS	STS	TOTAL	SCORE	AVERAGE SCORE	AVERAGE PERCENTAGE	CATEGORY
44	33	19	8	104	321	3.09	80,25%	Very High
36	40	13	12	104	308	2.96	77%	Very High
37	37	16	14	104	305	2.93	76,25%	Very High
45	34	15	10	104	322	3,12	81,5%	Very High
Average appreciation score							78,65%	Very High

Source: Data processed using SPSS 26

In the fourth question, 44 respondents expressed strong agreement, indicating that nearly half of the respondents greatly enjoy and understand the Islamic preaching content on YouTube. 33 respondents expressed agreement, with an average percentage of 80.25%, meaning they enjoy and understand the material, although not with maximum enthusiasm. 19 respondents expressed disagreement, with those disagreeing likely not feeling connected to the videos they watched. And 8 respondents expressed strong disagreement, firmly stating they do not enjoy or understand the material.

In the fifth question, 36 respondents expressed strong agreement. More than one-third of respondents stated that they strongly feel an increase in religious knowledge after watching Islamic preaching videos. 40 respondents expressed agreement with an average percentage of 77%. 16 respondents expressed disagreement, feeling they did not gain additional religious knowledge after watching Islamic preaching videos. And 12 respondents expressed disagreement, explicitly stating that Islamic preaching videos do not contribute to knowledge enhancement.

In the sixth question, 37 respondents expressed strong agreement, stating they greatly enjoy the process of listening to Islamic preaching material. 37 respondents expressed agreement with an average percentage of 76.25%, indicating respondents who also enjoy the videos, but not as intensely as those who strongly agree. 14 respondents expressed disagreement, showing discomfort or boredom with material presentation that is too normative, without contemporary context. They may feel that Islamic preaching on YouTube lacks emotional touch or is too formal. And 10 respondents expressed strong disagreement, indicating they do not feel enjoyment at all when listening to Islamic preaching material.

In the seventh question, 46 respondents expressed strong agreement, indicating that the majority feel Islamic preaching messages from YouTube can be very applicable in real life. 34 respondents expressed agreement with an average percentage of 81.5%. Respondents feel quite confident that the Islamic preaching videos watched are practically beneficial, although perhaps not all points can be directly implemented. 14 respondents expressed disagreement, with some respondents feeling that Islamic preaching messages cannot always be applied due to misalignment between Islamic preaching material and respondents' social/economic context. And 10 respondents expressed strong disagreement, with this group feeling they cannot apply Islamic preaching messages from YouTube at all, which deserves special attention.

Based on the recapitulation of four indicators forming the internalization variable, a final percentage of 78.65% was obtained. This figure falls within the very high category.

Table 3. Respondents' Responses to the Frequency Variable

4	3	2	1	TOTAL	SCORE	AVERAGE SCORE	AVERAGE PERCENTAGE	CATEGORY
15	10	43	31	104	217	2.53	54,25%	High
24	43	21	11	104	286	3.75	71,5%	High
36	36	18	16	104	305	2.93	76,25%	Very High
Average Frequency Score							71,16%	High

Source: Data processed using SPSS 26

In the eighth question, 43 respondents watch Islamic preaching videos twice a day, indicating that they feel sufficiently benefited by watching Islamic preaching videos twice daily. 10 respondents watch Islamic preaching videos three times and 15 respondents watch four times, showing a higher level of commitment and deeper engagement with the Islamic preaching material. And 31 respondents only watch Islamic preaching videos once a day, possibly because they feel it is sufficient or due to time constraints. With an average percentage of 54.25%.

In the ninth question, an average percentage of 71.75% was obtained. This figure indicates that generally, respondents watch Islamic preaching videos between 2 to 3 times per week, with a tendency approaching 3 times. This score indicates that respondents' level of engagement in watching Islamic preaching videos is quite high within a weekly period.

In the tenth question, an average percentage of 76.25% was obtained, with respondents watching more than once per week. This indicates that Islamic preaching videos are considered beneficial and highly relevant to most respondents, making them feel the need to repeat viewing more frequently. The most frequently chosen frequency is twice per week, showing that most respondents feel satisfied with watching Islamic preaching videos twice. There is also a group of respondents who watch more frequently, namely 3 or 4 times, indicating a higher level of need to understand and benefit from these Islamic preaching videos.

Based on the recapitulation results of three indicators used to measure the frequency variable, a final percentage of 71.16% was obtained. This result indicates that the frequency of activities conducted by respondents falls within the high category.

Table 4. Respondents' Responses to the Duration Variable

SS	S	TS	STS	TOTAL	SCORE	AVERAGE SCORE	AVERAGE PERCENTAGE	CATEGORY
34	33	16	21	104	276	2.65	71,25%	High
30	41	18	15	104	284	2.99	71%	High
36	44	11	13	104	291	3,09	72,75%	High
42	39	7	16	104	289	2.78	72,75%	High
Average Duration Score							71,25%	High

Source: Data processed using SPSS 26

In the eleventh question, with 34 respondents expressing agreement and 33 respondents expressing strong agreement, with an average percentage of 71.25%, this indicates that the majority of them spend more than 15 minutes per week watching Islamic preaching videos. A duration of more than fifteen minutes per week could include several short videos or one or two long-duration videos. This demonstrates that digital Islamic preaching videos are not only consumed sporadically or briefly. On the other hand, there are 16 respondents who disagree and 21 respondents who strongly disagree with spending more than 15 minutes per week watching Islamic preaching videos.

In the twelfth question, based on questionnaire results regarding the statement "In a day, I spend more than five minutes watching Islamic preaching videos on YouTube," 30 respondents strongly agreed, 41 respondents agreed, 18 respondents disagreed, and 15 respondents strongly disagreed. From this data, an average percentage of 71% was obtained. This figure indicates that the majority of respondents spend more than five minutes daily watching Islamic preaching videos on YouTube.

In the thirteenth question, based on questionnaire results regarding the statement "I do not limit my time when watching Islamic preaching videos on YouTube," 36 respondents strongly agreed, 44 respondents agreed, 11 respondents disagreed, and 13 respondents strongly disagreed. From the obtained data, the average percentage is 72.75%.

In the fourteenth question, based on questionnaire results regarding the statement "I watch Islamic preaching videos on YouTube until completion for every upload," 42 respondents strongly agreed, 39 respondents agreed, 7 respondents disagreed, and 16 respondents strongly disagreed. From this data, an average percentage of 72.25% was obtained.

Based on the recapitulation results of four indicators forming the duration variable, a final percentage value of 71.25% was obtained. This result indicates that the level of respondent involvement or participation in the measured activities falls within the high category.

B. Data Analysis Testing

1. Simple Linear Regression

Table 5. Simple Linear Regression Test Output
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	30.190	4.055		7.445	.000
	Video Dakwah	.289	.100	.274	2.881	.005

a. Dependent Variable: Noble Character

Source: Data processed using SPSS 26

In Table 5, the t-calculated value for the constant is 7.445, while the Islamic preaching video variable has a t-calculated value of 2.881, which is much smaller compared to the determined critical value. The significance value (sig) for the constant is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). On the other hand, the

significance value for the Islamic preaching video variable is 0.005, which is smaller than 0.05, with a t-table value of 1.983 obtained. The regression results show that the t-calculated value for the Islamic preaching video variable is 2.881 with a significance value of 0.005. Since t-calculated > t-table (2.881 > 1.983) and the significance value is less than 0.05, the alternative hypothesis H_a is accepted. This indicates that the Islamic preaching video variable has a significant effect on the noble character variable. Therefore, it can be concluded that the independent variable significantly influences the dependent variable.

2. Correlation Test

Table 6. T-Test Output
Correlations

		Islamic Preaching Videos	Noble Character
Video Dakwah	Pearson Correlation	1	.274**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.005
	N	104	104
Akhlikul Karimah	Pearson Correlation	.274**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	
	N	104	104

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Data processed using SPSS 26

Based on the table above, it can be observed that the significance value between Islamic preaching videos (X) and the formation of noble character (Y) is $0.005 < 0.05$, which means H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, indicating the presence of an influence between the two variables. The product moment correlation value shows a result of 0.274, which means it has a positive value and a weak relationship level, as it falls within the range of 0.20%-0.399%.

3. Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2)

The coefficient of determination test was conducted in this research to determine the magnitude of influence between variable (X) Islamic preaching videos and variable (Y) noble character. The following are the results of the coefficient of determination test using IBM SPSS 26.

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Output

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.368 ^a	.136	.101	6.874

a. Predictors: (Constant), Durasi, Frekuensi, Penghayatan, Perhatian

Source: Data processed using SPSS 26

Based on the table above, the coefficient of determination (R square) is 0.368, which means that the influence of Islamic preaching videos on noble character is 36.8%. This indicates that the magnitude of contribution from Islamic preaching videos to noble character formation is 36.8%. Meanwhile, the remainder represents contributions from other factors not examined in this research.

C. Discussion.

YouTube is a database containing Islamic preaching videos that are popular on social media and provides diverse information that is very helpful. With the presence of YouTube social media, the general public becomes more interested in learning something, because the packaging in audiovisual format will certainly be easily digestible and not boring to watch. By using YouTube, Da'wah Management students become more interested in continuously exploring academic studies related to subjects they are deepening, particularly in deepening Islamic studies that are very easily accessible on YouTube.

The statistical analysis results conducted show a consistent and significant relationship between Islamic preaching video consumption and positive changes in daily behavior. Students who consume Islamic preaching videos with high levels of understanding and engagement demonstrate positive changes. They become more courteous in speaking, more responsible in academic and organizational activities, and show empathy and care toward others.

Through analysis of four main variables: attention, internalization, frequency, and viewing duration. These four variables are used to describe the extent to which students are cognitively engaged in consuming digital Islamic preaching videos.

1. Attention

Based on the research conducted, a percentage of 78.5% was obtained. This indicates that students' level of attention toward Islamic preaching videos is quite high. The majority of respondents stated that they are more interested in watching Islamic preaching videos on YouTube compared to other social media platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, or Facebook. This demonstrates that YouTube is considered a more ideal platform for delivering Islamic messages in depth, as it supports the presentation of long-duration videos, easy search features, and a more comfortable interface for users. This pattern indicates that students consciously choose YouTube as

their primary medium for accessing Islamic preaching videos, showing a preference based on platform quality and convenience, not merely because of popularity.

Respondents also showed high interest in the visual design elements of Islamic preaching videos on YouTube, such as the use of graphics, colors, illustrations, and cinematography. These visual elements proved capable of enhancing students' attention to the Islamic content while making them more comfortable watching until completion. This proves that visualization in digital preaching plays an important role in attracting audience attention. Students do not only evaluate the sermon content from verbal material alone, but also from how it is presented visually. Islamic preaching that is packaged creatively and professionally is better able to compete amid the flood of other digital videos.

The majority of respondents also stated that they pay attention to every detail in the Islamic preaching videos they watch, from the message content, verses or hadiths presented, the preacher's expressions, to supporting illustrations or animations. This shows that students' attention is active and profound, not merely passive viewing. This pattern demonstrates that students as audiences possess the skills to filter information and absorb Islamic messages more critically. They do not only listen, but also evaluate and analyze video content, which can impact the internalization of religious values.

2. Appreciation

Based on the research conducted, a percentage of 78.65% was obtained. This indicates that Islamic Preaching Management students demonstrate the ability to absorb and contemplate the content of Islamic preaching videos they watch. Appreciation emerges when students feel that the video content touches their personal lives, such as discussing moral issues, spiritual motivation, or social-religious issues they face. The majority of respondents stated that they enjoy and are able to understand the Islamic preaching material delivered through YouTube. This shows that their attention is not merely passive, but active and focused. The combination of attractive visualization, preaching communication styles relevant to young generations, and ease of access becomes the main driving factor for students in devoting attention to the videos they watch. This pattern indicates that YouTube becomes an effective medium for Islamic preaching because it can create a religious learning atmosphere that is light yet meaningful. Students are more open to Islamic messages delivered with a relaxed yet scientific approach.

Respondents also felt that their religious knowledge increased after watching Islamic preaching videos on YouTube. This indicates that the attention given not only functions as focus while watching, but also produces understanding and accumulation of new knowledge. Students feel that they receive religious explanations contextually, which are easily accepted because they are delivered in communicative language. Thus, this attention pattern not only shows engagement while watching, but also impacts the enhancement of insight and motivation for religious learning.

The majority of respondents expressed that they feel enjoyment when listening to Islamic preaching material on YouTube. This comfort becomes an indication that attention toward Islamic

preaching videos is not formed due to obligation, but because of personal interest. When someone feels enjoyment, the process of delivering Islamic messages becomes more effective because it is not burdensome and is accepted voluntarily. This confirms that in the context of students, high attention is influenced by a pleasant atmosphere and down-to-earth preacher approaches.

Furthermore, students stated that the Islamic messages delivered in YouTube videos feel applicable and relevant to their daily lives. This shows that their attention emerges because Islamic preaching videos answer real problems they face. When Islamic preaching videos touch students' life realities, attention becomes deeper, even continuing to the application of those values. This pattern indicates that students do not only watch as a form of information consumption, but also as a means of self-reflection. Islamic preaching videos become a medium of contemplation that supports the process of religious character formation. This is highly relevant to their academic identity as future drivers of Islamic preaching in society.

3. Frequency

Based on the research conducted, a percentage of 71.16% was obtained. This indicates that the majority of students watch Islamic preaching videos regularly, with a frequency of 1-2 times per day. They usually access Islamic preaching videos through YouTube during their leisure time, such as after classes, before sleep, or when facing emotional pressure. The majority of respondents stated that they watch Islamic preaching videos at least once a day, either completely or partially. This shows that students' attention toward digital Islamic preaching has become part of their daily routine. This habit is formed actively, not due to academic obligation, but because of personal need for religious motivation and spiritual enlightenment. This pattern shows that Islamic preaching videos on YouTube have filled the space of students' media consumption that was previously perhaps dominated by entertainment or light content, indicating considerable attention toward religious content in their daily lives.

On a weekly scale, the majority of students watch Islamic preaching videos 2-3 times per week, showing consistency in searching for and consuming Islamic preaching videos. This frequency reflects that attention toward digital Islamic preaching is not merely impulsive, but has become a repetitive and continuous behavioral pattern. Students also stated that they are more active in watching Islamic preaching videos during leisure time, such as at night or on weekends, as well as when they need answers to life problems or require tranquility. This indicates that students' attention is highly contextual and responsive to their emotional or spiritual needs.

Many respondents also admitted to frequently rewatching the same Islamic preaching videos within a week, especially if the topic is highly relevant or delivered in a touching style. This rewatching behavior becomes an important indicator of deep attention, as it shows that students do not only absorb messages through a single viewing, but also want to strengthen their understanding or re-absorb the message content. Frequency in the form of repetition shows strong affective and cognitive engagement toward Islamic preaching videos, and becomes a signal that students have serious interest in deeper understanding, not just watching for entertainment or routine purposes.

This pattern reflects that Islamic preaching videos have become part of students' digital lifestyle, and are no longer just passive learning sources. Viewing frequency is also influenced by factors such as habits, religious interest, and ease of technological access.

4. Duration

Based on the research conducted, a percentage of 71.25% was obtained. This indicates that the duration of watching Islamic preaching videos varies, but the majority of students prefer short to medium-duration videos (approximately 15-25 minutes). They feel that long-duration videos (>30 minutes) tend to be boring or difficult to follow completely, unless the topic is very interesting or the speaker is well-known. Based on the questionnaire results, most students stated that they watch Islamic preaching videos at least once a day. Assuming one video lasts 5-15 minutes, students spend an average of 5 to 20 minutes per day watching Islamic preaching videos. This is a quite significant figure compared to other types of educational videos on YouTube. This duration indicates that students allocate special time in their daily lives to access and pay attention to sermon content or religious studies, showing that digital Islamic preaching is not merely a diversion, but part of a routine they consider important.

This phenomenon shows that moral and spiritual messages delivered in Islamic preaching videos are not only received passively, but are also internalized and practiced. This process aligns with cognitive psychology theory that explains how information received through media is processed in the mind, stored in memory, and then applied in actions.

A person's noble character is influenced by several factors, including attention, encoding (understanding and interpretation), storage (memory), retrieval, and application. These factors play an important role in shaping *akhlakul karimah* among Islamic Preaching Management students. In the communication process, particularly in message delivery through media such as Islamic preaching videos on YouTube, the effectiveness of delivery is not only determined by the message content, but also by how the message is processed cognitively by respondents. This cognitive process encompasses five important stages: attention, understanding, memory, retrieval, and application. These five aspects play a major role in determining the extent to which Islamic preaching messages can be understood, remembered, and implemented in respondents' daily lives. The following is an explanation of each of these stages:

1. Attention.

This represents the initial process in the cognitive system where an individual focuses their consciousness on specific stimuli from the environment. In the context of Islamic preaching, attention serves as the main gateway for information to be received by individuals. From the research results, Islamic Preaching Management students at IAIN Parepare tend to give more attention to Islamic preaching videos that are packaged attractively, for example through dynamic visual works, casual yet substantial language styles, and themes relevant to student life. This encourages students to follow videos repeatedly, thereby strengthening their exposure to Islamic values. This attention

becomes an important entry point in the character formation process. Without initial attention, Islamic preaching messages will not be processed further in the cognitive system.

2. Understanding

This is a cognitive process where information from Islamic preaching videos is organized and connected with knowledge or experiences previously possessed by students, namely by beginning to relate information from Islamic preaching videos to campus life such as attitudes toward lecturers, friends, organizations, preaching activities, and personal problems such as family conflicts, self-confidence, and identity searching. This understanding and interpretation process directly impacts the formation of noble character values within students, including increased moral awareness, especially related to social behavior such as speaking politely, keeping promises, and being honest. Empathy and patience increase, as students acknowledge better understanding the importance of controlling emotions and being kind to others. Motivation for change emerges, with many students beginning to improve themselves because they feel touched by messages they understand from videos.

3. Memory

Memory is the mental ability to receive, store, and retrieve information that has been learned or experienced by someone. Based on research results, students who watch Islamic preaching videos regularly at least 2-3 times per week show stronger tendencies in storing and remembering the content of Islamic preaching messages. The application of akhlakul karimah values appears in the form of real behavioral changes, such as being honest, trustworthy, and responsible.

4. Retrieval

This refers to an individual's ability to access information that has been stored in long-term memory again. Among Islamic Preaching Management students at IAIN Parepare, retrieval of religious information from YouTube Islamic preaching videos becomes one of the important indicators in seeing the extent to which these videos are not only understood and remembered, but also internalized in their religious consciousness. Several students stated that they always repeat some of the same videos so that messages from Islamic preaching videos can be remembered, enabling them to apply behaviors of honesty and devotion to Allah. This shows that these Islamic preaching messages have left traces in memory and can be accessed again at relevant times.

5. Application

This is the process of realizing knowledge or values that have been remembered into real actions. In this research, it was found that many students consciously change bad habits after regularly watching Islamic preaching videos, for example reducing harsh speech, beginning to be trustworthy, and being responsible as a reflection of values they learned from Islamic preaching videos.

Digital media, particularly YouTube, is not only a means of entertainment, but can also serve as a highly effective instrument for character education and moral preaching. Students who are familiar with technology more easily receive and absorb religious information that is packaged creatively and modernly. Islamic preaching videos provide space for reflection, learning, and personal value

formation. Thus, the process of character formation among Islamic Preaching Management students at IAIN Parepare through Islamic preaching videos can proceed more effectively and touch upon students' spiritual and moral aspects. Several factors that strengthen the influence of Islamic preaching videos on student character include:

1. Availability and Ease of Access.

YouTube can be accessed anytime and anywhere, allowing students to watch during their free time. In the context of research on the influence of YouTube Islamic preaching videos on the formation of *akhlakul karimah* among Islamic Preaching Management students at IAIN Parepare, this ease of access becomes one of the key factors that strengthens the effectiveness of digital preaching media. Students who have busy lecture schedules and various campus activities can still access Islamic preaching videos according to their free time, without having to be bound by specific space and time constraints. This flexibility allows them to rewatch videos if there are parts they do not fully understand, or to deepen material they feel is relevant to their daily lives. Furthermore, easy access to Islamic preaching videos through digital devices such as smartphones, tablets, and laptops makes the character formation process more contextual and continuous. Islamic preaching videos available on YouTube not only serve as sources of Islamic information, but also as means of self-reflection that can be accessed privately and freely. This contributes to the formation of noble character, as students can more easily be inspired by moral messages and spiritual values packaged in attractive and easily understood visual formats. Thus, YouTube as a preaching platform not only expands the reach of messages, but also increases opportunities for character transformation to occur gradually yet consistently.

2. Engaging Delivery Style.

Preachers who are communicative, use visual design works, or real stories make videos more memorable. In the context of this research, this delivery style becomes one of the important factors that determines the effectiveness of Islamic preaching messages. Preachers who are able to build virtual two-way communication, deliver material with lively intonation, and display attractive visuals, tend to be more successful in attracting attention and generating student interest. Additionally, the insertion of real stories or life experiences relevant to the Islamic preaching theme can touch students' emotional side, so that the delivered message is not only understood intellectually, but also absorbed emotionally and spiritually. This has a positive impact on the process of internalizing moral values and Islamic ethics that form the core of noble character. In the research, it was found that students more enjoy and understand Islamic preaching messages delivered with attractive and communicative styles, compared to delivery that is monotonous and overly theoretical.

The noble character formed from the influence of Islamic preaching videos reflects the success of digital preaching in internalizing Islamic values in a modern way. Preaching is no longer limited to mosque pulpits, but extends to digital spaces that have become virtual mosques for the younger

generation. With attractive, relevant, and touching approaches, Islamic preaching videos are able to touch hearts and shape character more than mere formal sermons. This shows that the combination of religious knowledge and technology can produce real moral transformation. The positive impacts of consuming Islamic preaching videos on YouTube on students' noble character include:

1. Changes in Attitude and Behavior

This research found that continuous consumption of Islamic preaching videos can encourage changes in attitude and behavior among students. These changes are evident from increased student awareness in living life according to Islamic values, both in aspects of worship, social ethics, academic responsibility, and self-control in facing problems. Students who previously tended to be indifferent toward religious obligations, after regularly watching Islamic preaching videos, began to show more religious behavior, such as being more disciplined in prayer, more selective in choosing social circles, and more polite and wise in their attitudes on campus and social media. From the research results, it was revealed that after listening to Islamic preaching on YouTube, they felt more motivated to introspect, improve bad habits, and emulate the noble character exemplified by the preachers. Therefore, it can be concluded that YouTube Islamic preaching videos play an important role in encouraging the process of value internalization, which gradually shapes positive attitudes and behaviors that reflect noble character in students' lives.

2. Increased Moral Awareness

This research found that one of the significant impacts of regular exposure to Islamic preaching videos is increased moral awareness among students. This moral awareness includes students' ability to behave well. Islamic preaching videos that present material about the importance of honesty, responsibility, tolerance, patience, and the importance of cultivating patience, become effective sources of moral learning. When these values are packaged in attractive visual forms and delivered with heart-touching approaches, students become more easily able to contemplate the delivered messages and relate them to their personal experiences.

Based on the findings above, it can be concluded that students show quite high interest in Islamic preaching videos on YouTube. They assess that the content of Islamic preaching videos is highly relevant to daily life and capable of answering the spiritual challenges they face. At the same time, the majority of respondents display a level of noble character that is categorized as good, characterized by honest, trustworthy, patient, tolerant, generous, humble, and responsible attitudes. This data shows that both variables have a harmonious initial relationship, where students who are more active in accessing and understanding Islamic preaching videos also show better moral quality.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings discovered, it can be concluded that the usage patterns of YouTube Islamic preaching videos among Islamic Preaching Management students at IAIN Parepare are influenced by several main variables: attention, appreciation, frequency, and duration. In terms of attention, an

average percentage value of 78.5% was obtained, which falls within the very high category. This indicates that respondents give considerable attention to the activities or materials being observed. From the appreciation aspect, an average percentage value of 78.65% was obtained, which falls within the very high category, reflecting that respondents not only pay attention, but are also able to appreciate the content or meaning of Islamic preaching videos delivered on YouTube. For frequency, an average percentage value of 71.16% was obtained, which is categorized as high, showing quite frequent engagement in watching Islamic preaching videos. And from the duration aspect, an average percentage value of 71.25% was obtained, also falling within the high category, reflecting the relatively consistent length of time in participation. YouTube Islamic preaching videos have a significant influence on the akhlakul karimah of Islamic Preaching Management students at IAIN Parepare. Based on the results of simple linear regression statistical calculations, the t-calculated value of 2.881 is greater than the t-table value of 1.983 at $n = 104$ $df = 0.05$.

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